

Table 2. Physicochemical and cooking qualities of 2 promising breeding lines.

Line	Milling outturn (%)	Chalkiness	L/B ratio	Size and shape	Amylose (%)	Protein (%)	Cooking time (min)	Tenderness
BR4290-3-1-10	72	1	3.8	MS	20.3	9.0	15.5	Soft
BR4290-3-3-5	72	0	3.5	MS	35.2	8.7	15.5	Medium
BR21 (susceptible check)	70	1	2.5	MB	27.0	7.9	18.0	Soft
Hashikalmi (local check)	71	3	2.4	MB	25.0	8.5	22.0	Soft

Heera, a super short-duration rice

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CR544-1-2, a 68 d duration selection from the cross CR404-48/CR289-1208, combines very short duration with high

yield potential. It was released as Heera in 1988 for cultivation in Orissa. Heera's parentage includes PTB18, PTB21, IR8, TKM6, and Assam Rice Collection material.

When direct seeded, Heera matures in 68-70 d in the wet season and in 75-77 d in the dry season.

Table 1. Performance of Heera (IET10973)^a in All India Coordinated Yield Trials, 1987 wet season.

IET no.	Culture or variety	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)			
			CRR1	Chiplima	Kanke	Hazaribag
10968	CR666-28	63	1.0	1.6	1.0	1.3
10970	Kalyani 2 (CR666-36-4)	61	0.6	0.8	1.2	1.4
10972	CR544-1-1	69	2.5	2.0	1.8	3.4
10973	Heera (CR544-1-2)	67	3.1	2.0	2.6	2.8
Local check		77	2.2	1.7	2.1	2.5

^aDirect seeded in rainfed fields.

It has semidwarf stature and green foliage. Grains are long bold with brown-colored husk and white kernel. Dormancy is about 15 d.

Heera is drought tolerant and resistant to gall midge, green leafhopper, blast, and rice tungro virus.

Yields are 2.5-3.5 t/ha when Heera is dry seeded in rainfed fields (other varieties with similar duration yield 1-1.5 t/ha). When pregerminated seeds are dibbled in puddled soil at 15- × 10-cm spacing, yields reach 4 t/ha (Table 1, 2).

Heera is suitable for drought-prone rainfed ricefields, for late planting in eastern India, and as a short-duration catch crop in southern and western India. ■

Table 2. Performance of Heera in farmers' field demonstration plots. Cuttack, India, 1989 wetseason.

Village and district	Yield (t/ha)
Khandeita, Cuttack	3.8
Rajanagar Patna, Cuttack	3.6
Aman Pada, Cuttack	3.6
Pratap Nagari, Cuttack	3.7
Pratap Nagari, Cuttack	3.6
Mugabhanga, Cuttack	4.5
Beltukuri, Kalahandi	3.7
Palsipani, Kalahandi	3.0
Palsipani, Kalahandi	2.4
Siritol, Kalahandi	2.1

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

TM8089, a new high-yielding, blast (Bl)-resistant upland rice

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TM8089, a derivative of the cross TKM7/IR8, is a short-duration (115 d), semi-dwarf (90 cm), Bl-resistant cultivar suitable for cultivation in sornavari (Apr-May), kar (May-Jun), kuruvai (Jun-Jul), and navarai (Dec-Jan) seasons in Tamil Nadu.

We evaluated TM8089 in eight station trials, six Rice Coordinated Yield Trials, seven Multilocation Trials, and 53 Adoptive Research Trials in 1984-85 and

11 trials in 1985-86. Mean grain yield was 5.5 t/ha, 6.2% higher than TKM9 and 21.8% higher than ADT36 (Table 1).

TM8089 is resistant to Bl under field conditions and moderately resistant under artificial screening (Table 2). It is moder-

ately resistant to sheath rot and glume discoloration (Table 2). Under field conditions, we found TM8089 moderately resistant to stem borer and gall midge and resistant to rice bug. TM8089 has moderate drought tolerance. ■

Table 1. Yield performance of TM8089. Tirur, India, 1981-86.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)			Increase (%) over	
	TM8089	TKM9	ADT36	TKM49	ADT36
Rice Research Station, Tirur (1981-88)	5.9	5.5	4.7	7.1	25.1
Rice Coordinated Yield Trials (1982-83)	4.7	-	4.1	-	14.1
Multilocation Trials (1983-84)	5.0	-	4.3	-	15.0
Adoptive Research Trials (1984-85)	5.3	4.4	4.7	21.4	14.2
Adoptive Research Trials (1985-86)	6.6	5.6	4.7	17.9	39.0